

WAYS OF FORMING READING COMPREHENSION IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *Reading is not an easy job in which the process of transcoding written speech into spoken speech and understanding the meaning of the read text are highlighted. These two types of reading are closely related and together make up "full reading". In the methodology, when forming the reading skill, it is customary to pay attention to such four components as: correctness, fluency, expressiveness and consciousness. First of all, it is necessary to distinguish semantic reading from technical reading, which is considered in works at the lessons of literary reading.*

Keywords: *reading, civilization, skill, education, analysis.*

Reading competency is a combination of knowledge and skills that allow a person to select, understand, organize information provided in sound and letter form, and successfully use it for public and personal purposes. This is how the new State Educational Standards define reading competency. This definition reflects the information-cognitive approach to reading, reading is considered as a kind of cognitive activity and is aimed at extracting information from texts, understanding and interpreting it. In this interpretation, the concept of "reading competency" is close to information competence. New standards attribute both of these types of competencies to meta-subject educational outcomes. The modern elementary school teacher has a clear goal - the education of a qualified, talented, creative reader. In modern society, the ability to read cannot be reduced only to mastering the technique of reading, it is a constantly evolving set of knowledge, skills, abilities, that is, the quality of a person that must be improved throughout his life in various situations of communication, activity.

Both domestic and foreign psychologists and teachers are studying this problem. According to studies carried out within the framework of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and The Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS), modern primary schoolchildren have difficulty in understanding what they read. Educational institutions set the tasks for the development and training of younger students. Following them, the teacher needs to formulate universal educational actions in students. Along with them, the most important result of mastering the main educational program is the formation of the skill of reading texts of different genres and styles.

First of all, it is necessary to distinguish meaningful reading from technical reading, which is considered in literary reading classes. Reading is a complex task that separates the process of transferring written speech to sound speech and understanding the meaning of the read text [32, p. 274]. These two types of reading are closely related to each other and together constitute "full reading" [58, p. 137-140]. Without mastering the mechanism of reading, it is impossible to understand the meaning of what is read, therefore, technical reading is only the sounding out of the text, while meaningful reading is primarily the study of one's own thoughts and understanding. M. Azimova considers the perception mechanism to be a "conflict of meanings" when the reader compares different options of perception of the reality reflected in the text [37, p. 117]. K.D.

Ushinsky, L.S. Vygotsky and other researchers emphasized this in their works [8, p. 58]. Today, in modern school practice, a lot of work is being done on the development of technical reading skills, often completely neglecting the formation of reading skills.

Although the entire course of literary study is aimed at understanding the meaning of the work. The development of mechanical reading is the first stage of mastering meaningful reading, which gradually turns into an effort to realize conscious reading, understanding what is read, and this eventually becomes the main goal of reading [32, p. 61]. The skill under consideration in learning to read literary texts is understood as understanding the moral idea of the work. Since in the literary text, not the words themselves, but their purpose in the text is important, the main goal of meaningful reading of the work is to derive its own meaning from the existing meanings in the text due to the existence of subjective meaning. Many researchers have recognized the important role of reading in the spiritual development of a person, but only if the reading is aimed at understanding and understanding. Some scholars consider meaningful reading as a type of cognitive process using the concept of "meaningful comprehension of the text".

The reading competence of elementary school students is the ability formed in children for targeted individual comprehension of books before reading, as they read and after reading the book. Today, it is important not only to give the child as much knowledge as possible, but to ensure his general cultural, personal and cognitive development, to equip him with such an important skill as the ability to learn. Reading competency is not running around the lines of the eye. The teacher's work to build reading competency is implemented in the following areas:

1. The formation of reading skills: the ability to read aloud and to oneself, knowledge of the main types of reading (introductory, in-depth, search, viewing). Techniques used: reading syllabic tables, speech workouts, game exercises to develop articulation, visual perception, attention, reading phrases with different semantic intonation, voice power, reading in pairs, working with tongue twisters, etc.

2. Readability. This competence includes the following components: knowledge of the studied works, understanding of literary concepts, their use and understanding; knowledge of books and works from the circle of children's reading offered in educational books for each class. Methods used: keeping readers' diaries, reading notebooks, making their own covers for the works of authors, little books, holding conferences, literary quizzes and festivals, staging works.

3. Ability to work with a book (definition and selection of books by genre, authors, topics, etc.); knowledge of the elements of the book. In work in this area, students work with reference books, dictionaries, and often visit libraries.

4. Skills and skills of actual reader activity, providing perception, interpretation (interpretation) and evaluation of a work of art as the art of a word, that is, according to the laws of this art (at a level accessible to schoolchildren of each year of study). The basis of this competence is versatile work with text.

Teachers who work with younger students know how difficult it is to teach children the technique of reading, but it is even more difficult to educate an enthusiastic reader. After all, to add words from letters and master the technique of reading does not mean becoming a reader. The main thing is to organize the process so that reading contributes to the development of the personality, and a developed personality feels the need for reading as a source of further development. The forms of work with the book are diverse and determined by the creativity of the teacher. Effective development of the reading interest of primary school students is facilitated by

conditions that include the systematic use of various forms of extracurricular activities, work with cultural institutions, and work with parents.

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